

TACTICAL ASPECTS OF A NEW VARIANT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF RECTAL PROLAPSE WITH DOLICHOSIGMA

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Abstract. Rectal prolapse of the entire thickness is a benign condition, which is defined as a circular protrusion of all layers of the rectal wall through the anal sphincter. Всего к настоящему периоду выполнено 38 подобных операций. A total of 38 such operations have been performed to date. The follow-up period for the patients was 4-6 months, the main advantages of the developed rectopexy method for rectal prolapses with dolichosigma are reliable fixation and reduction of the risk of recurrence of the disease, the likelihood of infection of the implant, deformation and narrowing of the colon anastomosis, and, consequently, passage disorders and progression of constipation.

Keywords: rectal prolapse; rectopexy; dolichosigma

Rectal prolapse to the full thickness is a benign condition, which is defined as a circular protrusion of all layers of the rectal wall through the anal sphincter [1]. So far, there is no substantial evidence of an advantage between perineal and abdominal access, or between resection or lack of resection in any access. In connection with the above, there is no doubt about the need to continue developing new technologies for surgical correction of the rectal prolapse. The task is to radically treat rectal prolapse and dolichosigma with the prevention of possible complications, prevention of the development of the adhesive process and scar deformation of the rectopexy zone.

The method is carried out as follows:

1. Laparotomy: inferior medial, transverse suprapubic (with intersection of rectus muscles), Pfannenstiel (transverse dissection of the skin and aponeurosis with dilution of rectus abdominal muscles).
2. Installation of an abdominal dilator for the exposure of the left colon.
3. Revision of the abdominal cavity: assessment of the state of the Douglas space, other pathological changes (liver/ gallbladder, colon, female genitalia, small intestine).
4. Dissection of the peritoneum on the right at the base of the mesentery of the sigmoid colon with a transition to the pelvic peritoneum.

5. Dissection of the peritoneum on the left along the white Toldt line in the direction of the pelvis without mobilization towards the splenic bend. The entrance to the retroperitoneal space, made by loose connective tissue. Blunt separation of the sigmoid arteries from retroperitoneal tissues, identification of the left ureter.
6. Determination of the inferior mesenteric vessels. Formation of a window in the mesentery behind the vascular pedicle. Identification of the hypogastric nerve and its preservation by posterior displacement. Blunt discharge behind the vascular bundle (avascular layer) to the entrance to the pelvis and complete mobilization of the rectum along the posterior semicircle along the Waldeyer fascia to the pelvic floor. To reduce the risk of damage to the pelvic autonomic nerves, it is necessary to avoid mobilization of the rectum to the sides.
7. Determination of resection boundaries: a. Distal (upper ampullary rectum): the anastomosis should be at the promontory level. b. Proximal: should take place in such a way that there is no excess of the sigmoid colon.
8. Gradual crossing of the mesentery (between the clamps with ligation) to the proximal point of resections.
9. Intersection of vessels: a. In most patients: standard ligation of the vascular pedicle (upper rectal artery) => before crossing, it is necessary to clarify the localization of the ureter. Formation of a window into the mesorectum at the distal edge of resection. Intersection and ligation of the mesorectum between the clamps. b. In patients with a history of perineal plastic surgery: with standard dressing, there is a risk of formation of the avascular portion of the intestine => correct operations: 1) Rectopexy only. 2) Resection of the sigmoid colon with the preservation of vascular arcades, i.e. the intersection of the mesentery in the immediate vicinity of the intestine. 3) Crossing of the intestine at the level of the anastomosis imposed earlier, with the removal of excess intestine and preservation of blood supply.
10. Rectopexy to a 6x10 cm mesh (polypropylene mesh): after mobilization of the rectum along the posterior surface, the implant is fixed to the promontory and presacral fascia with separate non-absorbable sutures; the mesh is wrapped around the rectum 360°, its edges are fixed on both sides with 3-4 sutures. It is possible to use laser exposure and composite coating.
11. An anastomosis of the descending part of the colon with the rectum is formed 2-3 cm below the fixation site with a mesh of the "end-side" type using a stitching device.
12. Drainage, suturing of the wound.

A total of 38 such operations have been performed to date. The follow-up period for the patients was 4-6 months. There is no data for a relapse of the disease. Advantages of the method: wrapping the intestine with a polypropylene mesh 360° during rectopexy contributes to a more reliable fixation of the rectum and prevents recurrence of the disease; the formation of an end-to-side anastomosis below the place of fixation of the rectum with a polypropylene mesh prevents the risk of infection of the implant; eliminates the risk of deformation and narrowing of the colon anastomosis, which in combination with the formation of an anastomosis below the place of fixation of the rectum significantly reduces in the postoperative period the violation of passage and, accordingly, the development or progression of constipation.

Thus, the main advantages of the developed method of rectopexy in MIC with dolichosigma are reliable fixation and reduction of the risk of recurrence of the disease, the likelihood of infection of the implant, deformation and narrowing of the colo-rectoanastomosis, and, consequently, passage disorders and progression of constipation.

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